

Survey on the deployment model of a Clinical Data Management System under development (VISTA Trials)

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1 Abstract

Background: Academic clinical trials units have traditionally maintained their Clinical Data Management Systems (CDMS) on their own premises or those of their parent organisation (e.g. university). There is growing use, however, of 'SaaS' or 'Software as a Service' systems, in which the CDMS is hosted externally by another organisation and access from the trials unit is web-based. ECRIN is supporting the development of a new CDMS ('Vista Trials') by EORTC, which will only offer a SaaS based deployment model. Because opinions vary widely about the suitability of the SaaS model, ECRIN felt it was important to clarify the acceptability of such a system to academic trials units.

Methods: An online survey was created, using 'Survey Monkey', and sent to 129 academic trials units in Europe. After asking for brief details about the unit and existing systems, the survey asked how acceptable the proposed SaaS deployment method would be and why, and explored factors that would make the deployment more or less attractive.

Results: 53 trials units responded from 14 countries (41.1%). The proposed SaaS deployment model was acceptable to 53% of respondents, with smaller units, and those interested in changing their current system, relatively favourable to the model. Key factors appeared to be views on data security and data access but many others were mentioned. Some opinions were relatively dogmatic – 8 units claimed SaaS was essential for them whilst 11 rejected it as 'a matter of principle'. There also seemed some confusion about regulatory compliance of SaaS based systems: 44% saw no problem, 19% identified an issue and 37% were not sure.

Conclusions: The range of opinions expressed about SaaS implies a similar range in the assumptions units have about this type of deployment, e.g. about the security and access implications. Coupled with the uncertainties over compliance, this indicates a need for organisations like ECRIN to work with regulators, system vendors, hosting organisations, and trials units to clarify the risks and issues. This would inform the future development of the SaaS model for clinical trials systems, and help individual units make decisions about the best way of managing their CDMS.

2 Keywords

Clinical trial, Clinical Data Management System (CDMS), survey, European Clinical Research Infrastructures Network (ECRIN), European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), deployment, hosting, data management

3 Background

The use of a specialist Clinical Data Management Systems (CDMS) to handle the data that must be collected, processed and analysed in a clinical trial, to maximise data quality and to support the conduct of that trial, is increasingly seen as essential. Consequently, CDMS are in routine use in more than 90% of academic trial units (1). A large variety of commercial, locally developed and open source systems are used, with no system achieving widespread use so far. This considerable and continuing heterogeneity of CDMS can hinder international cooperation and clinical trial data exchange, underlining the need to implement common data standards like the ODM (Operational Data Model) from CDISC (the Clinical Data Interchange Standard Consortium) (2). In addition, using commercial CDMS software can result in other problems for academic research units, because of high costs and because of risks concerning delivery and future software maintenance.

The current unsatisfactory situation motivated ECRIN (European Clinical Research Infrastructures Network, see Appendix 1) and EORTC (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer, see Appendix 1) to initiate the development of a professional and efficient CDMS tool for multinational clinical trials performed by academic clinical trial units (3). The system:

- is based on the VISTA Trials system previously developed and routinely used by EORTC, but with considerable adaption and reprogramming.
- uses international standards, especially CDISC ODM, and ECRIN requirements. Adoption of standards is a prerequisite for supporting population-based studies, registries or EHR systems data mapping.
- will be maintained and supported by EORTC in cooperation with ECRIN
- will offer non-profit fees for the use of the tool and services, to trials units associated with ECRIN also for non-EORTC clinical trials and outside oncology.
- Is flexible enough to cope with the wide variety of data types and data sources used in modern clinical trials, e.g. from bio-sample analysis, genetics, and imaging as well as traditional clinical assessment. This will support modern clinical trials based on extensive translational research with treatment fit for a particular disease and molecular profile (personalised medicine, precision medicine).

Software development is performed within the currently EU-funded ECRIN-IA project by EORTC and testing is carried out by three pilot centres belonging to ECRIN (Düsseldorf, Marburg, Copenhagen) (4). Testing of all versions is against the list of functionality provided by EORTC and against the ECRIN-requirements. The new VISTA Trials tool is expected to be available in 2015. It will provide four main modules: Study definition, Clinical data collection, System management and Reports (for more information see: <http://vistatrials.org>).

The database and web servers running a typical CDMS system can sit within the trials unit itself, or be sited within the unit's host's (e.g. university) central IT systems, or be hosted externally, in either another academic or clinical environment or within a commercial hosting system. All these different deployment models are currently used by academic trial units, and there is much discussion about the pros and cons of each.

EORTC plans to provide VISTA trials only as an externally hosted system, i.e. as Software as a Service (SaaS). All parts of the system will be fully web based and accessible from anywhere. There will therefore be no local installation, with only one instance of VISTA trials being deployed at any

particular time. At the beginning VISTA trials will be hosted on EORTC servers. When sufficient user numbers are reached, it will be moved to a third party hosting / application management facility ensuring continued professional management for a larger user community.

Software creators and users are increasingly embracing cloud based technologies and deployment models (as witnessed by the widespread adoption of Office 365 and Google apps) and many CDMS providers are adapting their solutions to this new environment. It allows websites to be more responsive and serve a range of clients and devices, and it can also better support the increasing need for patient-centric trials and electronic patient reported outcomes. The difficulty is that there exists, anecdotally, a range of concerns within clinical trials units about the security and regulatory implications of such an approach, and there is a lack of empirical data about the attitude of academic trials units, as a whole, towards a CDMS-deployment model based on external hosting. It was therefore felt necessary to perform a survey within the ECRIN community on this important issue.

4 Objective of the survey

The survey was designed to find out how acceptable the planned VISTA Trials deployment model would be to trials units linked to ECRIN, and what factors would be important in making the system more or less attractive to potential customers. By implication, not least because Vista Trials itself has not yet been released, the survey was intended to assess the attitudes of trial units to the remote hosting of CDMS services in general.

In addition to specific questions about VISTA trials deployment, basic data about the data management activity of the participating trial units was collected in order to link trial unit characteristics (e.g. size, satisfaction with current CDMS) to statements about VISTA trials deployment.

5 Methods

Survey design

This was an online survey with a questionnaire developed by ECRIN and EORTC and implemented by S. Canham using the “survey monkey” tool (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/>). Appendix 2 provides a listing of the survey’s questions.

The survey questionnaire link was distributed by European Correspondents (EuCos) to trial units performing data management in clinical trials and belonging to national clinical trial networks linked to ECRIN-IA (see the Description of Work from 2013-11-05) (4). Trial units from UK and Ireland, where there was not an active European Correspondent in post, were also invited to participate in the survey. In summary, 129 trial units in 19 countries were asked to participate in the survey.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected by “survey monkey” was exported into CSV format and imported into R for analysis. The data were analysed with R (version 3.1.2) by A. Vogt (KKS Düsseldorf) with the support of S. Canham and C. Ohmann. Variables for analysis included the country of the trial unit, baseline characteristics of trial units (questions 3-8) and specific questions about VISTA deployment (questions 9-20) (see Appendix 3). Statistical analysis was performed according to the Statistical Analysis Plan created by C. Ohmann and agreed with EORTC before the survey began.

The analysis was descriptive with univariate statistics for individual questions and cross tables for selected questions. For free text variables a qualitative analysis was performed.

6 Results

A detailed report of the results is available in Appendix 3.

Response to survey

The online questionnaire was open between 27 January and 6 March 2015. Two reminders were sent to the trial units by the EuCos. Data were entered into the online questionnaire between 28 January and 5 March 2015.

From the 129 trial units that were invited to participate in the survey, 56 responded (response rate: 43.4%). Two units gave no information apart from their affiliation and one unit answered only one question. This leaves 53 units for analysis (response rate: 41.1%). Nearly half of the responses were received from Germany (n=15) and UK (n=11) (49%). Participation was exceptionally high in Germany (75% response rate).

Data management activity of trial units

Table 1 gives an overview on the involvement of trial units in current data management trials (DM trials). Around half of the units started less than 5 DM trials in 2013 (43%) and recruited less than 500 subjects in DM trials (51%). The overwhelming majority of the trial units (80 %) were rather small with between 1 and 5 data managers. Three larger trial units participated with two units employing more than 20 data managers.

DM Trials / Year started in 2013 ¹	Trial units, N (%)
<5	20 (43)
5-9	12 (26)
>= 10	15 (32)
Total	47 (100)
Num. of Subjects recruited in DM trials in 2013 ²	Trial units, N (%)
<100	10 (27)
100-499	9 (24)
500-999	8 (22)
>= 1000	10 (27)
Total	37 (100)
Number of DM staff currently employed ³	Trial units, N (%)
1-5	40 (80)
6-10	7 (14)
11-20	1 (2)
>20	2 (4)
Total	50 (100)

Table 1: Data management workload in trial units participating in the survey. Missing data: ¹6 units, ²16 units, ³3 units

Clinical Data Management Systems (CDMS) in use

In summary, 47 units listed their current CDMS systems in use, and another two stated explicitly that they had no CDMS at all. 46 units provided information about the location of their systems and 43 provided meaningful data on the relative proportion of studies using each system. 84 system installations were reported. Location information was available for 81 of these, and usage data was available for 74.

The data are summarized in table 2. Of the 84 systems reported, approximately half are commercial (48%), 20% are open source products and 14% in-house solutions. No single system is used in the majority of the trial units. 12 units are using in-house systems. Among the commercial systems Macro is used most often (n=12), followed by SecuTrial (n=5). OpenClinica and RedCap have 7 and 6 users respectively. For all the other systems less than 5 applications were reported.

From those units providing the location of the systems (n=81), 41 % reported use within their own unit, 33% within their parent university or hospital and 26% hosted the system externally by another organisation (see Appendix 3 for detailed information).

System Type	Units Using N (%)	Installation Location*		
		Own unit N	Parent Univ./ Hospital N	Externally Hosted N
General tool	9 (11)	5	3	1
Commercial	40 (48)	15	13	11
Open source	17 (20)	7	5	4
In-house	12 (14)	6	5	1
Unknown	6 (7)	0	1	4
Total	84	33	27	21
		41%	33%	26%

Table 2: Type of systems currently in use with location of use. *3 locations missing

In Table 3 the attitude towards a new CDMS and external hosting is summarized. One quarter of the survey participants are definitely interested (25%) and nearly half are possibly interested (47%) in evaluating a new system.

Level of Interest in evaluating a new CDMS system in the next 18 months ¹	Trial units N (%)
Not interested	14 (27)
Possibly interested	24 (47)
Definitely interested	13 (25)
Total	51 (100)

Table 3: Level of Interest in a new system.

Around 1/5 of the participants think that there are rules and regulations preventing external hosting (19%), with the reasons given including possible hosting outside EU (n=2), local rules of university/hospital (n=2), sponsor requirements (n=1), data protection laws (n=3), ISO requirements (n=1) and GCP (n=1). Even within countries there was tremendous variation in responses. This, coupled with the high proportion of units (> 1/3) who answered 'unknown' to this

question indicates that there is considerable confusion about this issue within the clinical trial community.

Rules and regulations preventing external hosting ²	N* (%)
Yes	10 (19)
No	23 (44)
Unknown	19 (37)
Total	52 (100)
Assessment of the proposed deployment model ¹	N* (%)
Yes	27 (53)
No	24 (47)
Total	51 (100)

Table 4: Attitude towards a new CDMS and external hosting; missing data: ¹2 units, ²1 unit

Specific questions about VISTA deployment

More than half of the participants see the VISTA deployment model as a viable option (53%; see table 4). Nearly all the units who are definitely interested in replacing their current system agree with the proposed deployment model of VISTA (12/13). For those who are possibly interested in replacing their current system, the agreement with the deployment model is around 50%.

In Table 5, the reasons for not accepting the proposed deployment model as a viable option are summarized. All the pre-listed concerns were reported as significant, with worries about security of the data being the most common (63%).

Reasons for not accepting the proposed deployment model as a viable option	N (%)
Worries about the security of the data	15 (63)
Concern over total costs, compared to installation locally	11 (46)
Fears we might lose control over data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)	13 (54)
As a matter of principle or policy, we do not want our data stored by another organisation	13 (54)
Uncertainties about compliance with data protection requirements	12 (50)
Other	10 (42)
Total	24

Table 5: Reasons for not accepting the proposed deployment model

The views of trial units who considered the deployment as a viable option are provided in table 6. For 8 units (30% of this subgroup) the deployment model is seen as essential, for 6 units (22%) the model is not essential but attractive. Around half of this group (52%) would evaluate VISTA like any other CDMS system. 11% would prefer a local installation.

Views from trial units accepting the SaaS deployment model described for VISTA trials	N (%)
The model is essential for us because we have no local IT systems; including hosting with Vista Trials makes the system an attractive option	8 (30)
The model is not essential but would make the system more attractive to us than a system we needed to support directly ourselves	6 (22)
The model presents no problem – we would evaluate Vista like any other CDMS system.	14 (52)
The model would make the system less attractive to us – but we would still be willing to investigate Vista Trials as a potential system	6 (22)
The model would allow us to try out the system for a few trials but for long term use we would want to move the system 'in-house'. (Please note – local installation of Vista Trials is not currently planned as an option)	3 (11)
Other	3 (11)
Total	27

Table 6: Views expressed by units accepting the proposed deployment model

As shown in Table 7, the most important factors that would make the deployment model attractive are clear assurances and information on data security (75%), assurances of confidentiality of data (71%), clear assurances and information on data access (67%) and cheaper costs of SaaS versus local installation (53%). Interestingly one third of the trial units are opting for a local installation of VISTA trials (33%).

Factors making the proposed deployment model more attractive.	N* (%)
Cheaper costs of SaaS versus local installation	27 (53)
Convenience of outsourcing management	19 (37)
Ease of experimenting with/assessing the system	20 (39)
Clear assurances and information on data security	38 (75)
The option of local installation after initial trials of the system (Please note – local installation of Vista Trials is not currently planned as an option)	17 (33)
Clear assurances and information on data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)	34 (67)
Assurances of confidentiality of data	36 (71)
Other	11 (22)
Total	51

Table 7: Factors that would make the SaaS model more attractive. Missing data: *2 units

Prerequisites for trial units to use VISTA trials as SaaS are shown in table 8. The overwhelming majority see compliance of the SaaS service provider with the host's national regulatory standard (80%) and SLAs backed up by liabilities/penalties (78%) as essential. More than half voted for the possibility of performing an external audit of the SaaS provider (60%).

Around half of the survey participants would prefer a single standard license independent of usage (48%), around 1/5 a user fee model involving small-medium-large packages (18%) or licence fees calculated from the number of trials (18%) – see table 9.

Prerequisites for using VISTA trials as SaaS*	N (%)
Service Level Agreements (SLAs) backed up by liabilities/penalties	39 (78)
Compliance of SaaS service provider with the host's national regulatory standard	40 (80)
The possibility of performing external audit of the SaaS provider by any Vista Trials user	30 (60)
Other	6 (12)
Total	50

Table 8: Prerequisites for using VISTA trials as SaaS. Missing data: *3 units

Preference of trial units for license pricing models*	N (%)
A single standard licence (i.e. independent of usage)	24 (48)
User fee model proposing small-medium-large packages. Each package will allow Vista Trials to be used for a maximum number of clinical studies and/or recruited patients per year.	9 (18)
Licence fees calculated from the number of trials on the system	9 (18)
Licence fees calculated from the number of CRF-data pages/items on the system	5 (10)
Other	3 (6)
Total	50

Table 9: Preference for licensing pricing models. Missing data: *3 units

Involvement of ECRIN in VISTA trials

The involvement of a committee, consisting of an equal number of representatives from EORTC and ECRIN, that would be responsible for updated specifications, proposed modifications, further version releases and the non-profit fees, would help to make the deployment model more attractive for the majority of survey participants (60%) (see table 10).

Role of the CDMS-Committee for the attractiveness of the deployment model ¹	N (%)
Yes	31 (60)
No	21 (40)
Total	52

Table 10: Attitude towards joint ECRIN-EORTC management . Missing data: ¹1 unit, ²3 units

Nearly 3/4 of the trial units of the ECRIN community would be interested to provide feedback on the use of VISTA and to suggest improvement after the ECRIN-IA project has finished (72%). A

little less than 2/3 of the participants would like to have ECRIN involved in providing user support (63%).

Interest of trial units in providing feedback on the use of VISTA ²	N (%)
Yes	36 (72)
No	14 (28)
Total	50
Attractiveness of involvement of ECRIN in user support ¹	N (%)
Yes	33 (63)
No	19 (37)
Total	52

Table 11: Attitude towards involvement of ECRIN . Missing data: ¹1 unit, ²3 units

7 Discussion

The response rate of our online survey (41.1%) is above the average of usual online surveys (e.g. 33%, see (5)). This is similar to two surveys ECRIN performed in 2007 (response rate: 47%) and 2008/2009 (response rate: 43%) (1). Interestingly, nearly 50% of the responses in this survey were received from two countries (Germany, UK). The response rates per country show remarkable differences.

The DM workload of the trial units covered in the survey varies tremendously between very large units, performing DM in a considerable number of trials with high recruitment targets, and small units who support only a very few trials.

Within this survey the current use of CDMS systems in trial units was assessed. This information can usefully be compared with the ECRIN surveys performed in the past (1). The rate of CDMS systems in routine use was similar between these surveys (95%, 83%) and our current survey (96%), demonstrating that the use of such systems can be seen as a standard. No major differences were observed for the use of commercial systems (48%/59% versus 48%). There were, however, less locally developed systems (38%/32% versus 25%) but more open source systems (10%/6% versus 20%) in use now. The heterogeneity of commercial systems in routine use has not changed over the years. The leading commercial CDMS in all surveys is InferMed's MacroTM. No other specific system was used more than 10 times in any of the surveys. This indicates that no individual system could really dominate the market for academic trial units linked to ECRIN. If we look at open source systems, OpenClinicaTM and RedCapTM, which were not used/not available in 2007, are on the rise with 7 and 6 users respectively in this survey. It will be interesting to see if the open-source model continues to gain acceptance in the future.

Trying to capture this data by periodic surveys is highly inefficient and will always result in partial data. It would be far better if there was a permanent 'index' of academic trials units carrying out data management activities that provided some information about the systems they were using and where they were hosted, together with an approximate indication of their relative size / activity. Such an index could be posted on a web site and updated by the trials units themselves. ECRIN would be very interested in discussing this idea with national networks and others, to

clarify how such an index could best be established and maintained, as well as the nature of the detailed information it should contain.

Three quarter of the units participating in our survey seem to be dissatisfied with their current situation, given that they are definitively interested (27%) or possibly interested (47%) in evaluating a new CDMS system in the next 18 months, to replace some or all of their existing CDMS functionality.

Of utmost importance, in effect the central question of the survey, is whether the SaaS deployment model would be a viable option for academic trial units. Here the survey response is split roughly equally, with a slight predominance for viewing the specified SaaS deployment approach (53%) as viable. Nearly all units definitely interested to replace their CDMS system agree with the proposed deployment model compared to around 50% from those who are possibly interested.

Units with smaller workload, measured by the number of trials supported, are more favourable to the deployment model in comparison with larger units (see additional file 2). Of specific interest is the response of two of the largest units (more than 20 data managers), which are not in favour of the deployment model. This is underlined by free text comments from one of these units, stating that they have in place all they required and that EORTC had first to show that they were able to support the full trial lifecycle as well as being able to provide long-term commitment.

Local installations are not foreseen in the VISTA deployment model so far. Nevertheless, one third of the trial units (33%) see the option of a local installation as an important factor in making the deployment model more attractive. Even amongst those units who considered the SaaS deployment model as a viable option, three would like the option to move it in-house. One trial unit explicitly expressed the wish to have a data centre located in their country.

Trials units not seeing the VISTA deployment model as a viable option for own usage had various concerns. More than half of these units had worries about security of the data (63%), and / or feared losing control over data access (54%), and / or did not want 'their' data stored by another organisation (54%) or had uncertainties about compliance with data protection requirements (50%). In the free text comments further issues were introduced: missing information on costs, staffing, software updates, security/confidentiality, access to data, participation of regulatory bodies, SLA/vendor audit. This spectrum of concerns reflects much of what was recently discussed in an ECRIN workshop on cloud computing and clinical trials (6).

Trial units with a positive attitude towards the VISTA deployment model include 30% classifying the VISTA approach as essential and attractive and 22% as not essential but attractive. Nevertheless, around half of this subgroup stated that they would evaluate the VISTA system like any other system, which clearly underlines the need for VISTA Trials to exhibit quality comparable to other systems already in routine use.

What would make the proposed VISTA deployment model more attractive? Here, clear preferences were expressed by the survey participants: clear assurances and information on data security (75%), assurances of confidentiality of data (71%) and clear assurances and information on data access (67%). Factors like cheaper costs of SaaS versus local installation and convenience of outsourcing management are more attractive to those trial units who are in favour of the deployment model compared to those who are not. In the individual free text responses several other features were mentioned as increasing the attractiveness of the system, including the ability to have additional features in the software, making the code open source, a development

roadmap influenced by users, vendor long-term commitment, the possibility of vendor audits and more information being available on the software. There is high level of agreement in the survey on necessary prerequisites for using VISTA trials as SaaS. The overwhelming majority, independent of whether they are advocates of the deployment model or not, see the compliance of the SaaS service provider with the host's national regulatory standard (80%) and SLAs backed up by liabilities and penalties (78%) as essential. More than half of the survey participants (60%) would like to have the possibility of performing an external audit of the SaaS provider. There is a preference of the trial units for a single standard license model independent of usage (48%), with less interest in licence models based on usage. There is clear preference for user support to be included in the user fee as part of a single package (84%, see additional file 2).

Within the trials units surveyed there was strong interest in supporting the VISTA tool. The overwhelming majority of survey participants (72%) would be willing to provide feedback on the use of VISTA trials and to suggest improvements of the system after the ECRIN-IA project. The SaaS deployment model is also seen as more attractive if ECRIN is involved in user support (e.g. in providing a helpdesk, on-site training, and online training material). The majority of survey participants (60%) supported the idea of a CDMS committee, consisting of representatives from EORTC and ECRIN, to be responsible for updated specifications, proposed modifications, further version releases and the non-profit fees in the future. In summary therefore the survey reinforced the idea that ECRIN should have a role in supporting VISTA Trials after the ECRIN-IA project is completed.

8. Conclusions

The assumption is that the views expressed for and against a SaaS based deployment model, and the specific reasons cited for them, are generally applicable and do not reflect specific views about EORTC or Vista Trials. The most obvious feature, though not unexpected, is the very wide range of opinion expressed about the proposed deployment method. Some units (n = 8) are committed to a SaaS based model and external hosting because they have no local IT provision at all, whilst at the other extreme 13 units state 'as a matter of principle or policy' that they do not want their data stored by another organisation. Other units are less dogmatic but at the moment a further 11 still see the model as a non-viable option, whilst a further 19 units would find the model acceptable, albeit with varying levels of enthusiasm.

Increasing understanding around some of the key concerns (security, access, data protection etc.), identifying ways to alleviate risks and developing mechanisms to assure sponsors, researchers and regulatory bodies that data management is compliant with GCP principles, may all increase the acceptance of external hosting of data. It should certainly help individual units make decisions about any specific system deployment proposal and, where external hosting is used, help to ensure its security and integrity. To that end ECRIN plans to hold more workshops on external hosting of clinical trial data, whether that uses 'cloud' based facilities or more traditional externally managed services. ECRIN is also intending to extend its existing set of standards in IT and data management to more clearly cover the case when data is stored and managed remotely. A key question asked respondents if they felt there were 'local, national or institutional rules and regulations' that would prevent an externally hosted service. Although 44% of respondents said 'No' a substantial minority (19%) said Yes and 37% said they did not know. Interestingly opinions on this varied within countries as well as between them, indicating a level of confusion about this issue. It will be important to engage with regulatory authorities, perhaps within the context of the ECRIN workshops mentioned above, to try and clarify the regulatory position on external hosting, and then disseminate this information as widely as possible.

The use of externally hosted services for trials data will almost certainly increase in the future, as cloud based storage becomes more familiar generally and the potential economic attractions of the SaaS model – to both vendors and purchasers – become more apparent. It is also clear that while some members of the trials community have already embraced this model most – quite understandably – are cautious about the idea of externally hosted data, and would seek clear assurances on regulatory issues, as well as questions of access, control, cost and security (amongst others) before being willing to use such a system. There is a need for organisations like ECRIN to work with regulators, system vendors, trials units and networks to clarify the various risks and issues so that appropriate guidance can be made available.

9 List of Abbreviations

CDMS =	Clinical Data Management System
DOW =	Description of Work (related to EU-funded projects)
ECRIN =	European Clinical Research Infrastructures Network (see: www.ecrin.org)
ECRIN-IA =	ECRIN- Integrated Activity (EU FP7-funded project, 2012-2015 grant no. 284395, see: www.ecrin.org)
EORTC =	European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (see: www.eortc.be)
EuCo =	European Correspondent (national contact point for ECRIN partner countries)
KKS =	Koordinierungszentrum für Klinische Studien (Coordination Centre for Clinical Trials) (see: www.kks-netzwerk.de)
SaaS =	Software as a Service
SLA =	Service Level Agreement

10 Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

11 Author's contributions

The survey was planned and conducted by CO and SC. The online questionnaire was developed with input from CO, SC, JD (ECRIN) and PR (EORTC) and implemented by SC. Analysis was performed by AV with support from CO and SC. CO and SC conceived the manuscript.

12 Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank the European Correspondents from the countries involved in ECRIN-IA for identifying trial units in their country involved in data management, distributing the survey material to the units and for supporting response by answering questions and sending reminders. ECRIN-IA is partially funded by the European Commission (FP7 284395, Theme INFRA-2011-1.1.5.)

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Appendix 1 - Organisations involved in developing VISTA trials

European Clinical Research Infrastructures Network (ECRIN)

In 2013 ECRIN was awarded the status of European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), a legal status designed to facilitate the joint establishment and operation of research infrastructures of European interest. ECRIN is a distributed infrastructure supporting multinational clinical research in Europe. ECRIN was developed and matured through the support of the European Union FP6 and FP7 programmes in a series of projects. Currently there are 7 member countries in ECRIN-ERIC, the management office is located in Paris.

ECRIN offers integrated support to multinational clinical research projects through information, consultancy, and a set of flexible services, for any category of clinical research, in any medical field. This support is provided by the distributed infrastructure connecting national ECRIN partners (networks of Clinical Research Centres or Clinical Trials Units). **Information** is provided by the network of ECRIN European Correspondents, **Consultancy** is provided by experts from the national ECRIN partners and coordinated by the European Correspondent and **Services** are coordinated by the ECRIN European correspondents and provided by national ECRIN partners at not-for-profit rates for academic trials. Provision of services requires submission of the protocol to the ECRIN Scientific Board, coupled to a logistical assessment of the project. (see <http://www.eclin.org>)

ECRIN-Integrating Activity (ECRIN-IA) (Grant agreement no: 284395)

ECRIN-IA (2012-2015) is the fourth step of the ECRIN programme, funded by the FP7 Infrastructure programme. Networking activities promote pan-European expansion, capacity building, and partnership with other world regions, and address the funding issue (Work Package 2). ECRIN-IA develops e-services, education material to train professionals and patients associations, and communication with users, patients, citizens and policymakers (WP3). It supports the structuring and connection to ECRIN of disease-, technology-, or product-oriented investigation networks and hubs focusing on specific areas: rare diseases (WP4), medical device (WP5), and nutrition (WP6).

Transnational access activities support the cost of multinational extension of clinical trials on rare diseases, medical device and nutrition selected by the ECRIN scientific board (WP7). Joint research activities are designed to improve the efficiency of ECRIN services, through the development of tools for risk-adapted monitoring (WP8), and the upgrade of the EORTC VISTA data management tool (WP9). (see <http://www.eclin.org>)

European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC)

The European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (**EORTC**) is a pioneer in promoting multi-disciplinary cancer clinical research and pan-European collaboration and links a network of more than 2,500 clinicians and scientists in more than 300 hospitals in over 30 countries. The EORTC is a non-profit international research organisation created under Belgian law in 1962. It encompasses all aspects of cancer research, from translational research and new drug development to large phase III clinical trials and meta-analyses. EORTC Headquarters in Brussels handles some 30 protocols that are permanently open to patient entry, over 50,000 patients who are in follow-up, and a quality assured database of more than 180,000 patients. The scientific activities of EORTC are strictly peer-reviewed and subject to quality assurance/ quality control programs. The EORTC operates on an independent basis, and in this capacity is able to work in partnership with the pharmaceutical industry in evaluating innovative molecules (see <http://www.eortc.org/>)

Appendix 2 – Survey questions

(This appendix lists the questions but does not attempt to duplicate the layout and formatting within Survey Monkey.)

Part A: Your Unit

Respondent Details

1a. Unit Name

1b. Parent University and / or Hospital

1c. City, Country

Please provide the following, as we may wish to contact you to clarify your responses

2a. Respondent Name

2b. Role

2c. Email address

Data Management Activity

In this section please consider only the trials where your unit provided, or is providing, *data management services*, e.g. designing the database and CRFs, collecting the data, managing user access to data, managing queries, and extracting data.

N.B. For questions 3 - 5 answers should be integer numbers.

3. Considering your *current* 'data management trials', how many have recruitment targets of...

0-50	51-200	201-1000	>1000

4. How many data management trials (all sizes) did you *start* in each of the following years?

2012	2013

5. Approximately how many subjects did you recruit in each of the following years within your data-management trials?

2012	2013

6. How many staff do you have working as data managers (full time equivalents)? This would exclude purely IT staff.

1-5	6-10	11-20	>20

Current systems

7. Which clinical database management systems do you currently use? Please list all, including any developed 'in-house'.

For each system, please also indicate the approximate *percentage* of your trials supported by that system, and where the system (i.e. the production servers) is *physically located*:

- within your own unit (U),
- within your parent university or hospital's central systems (P)
- hosted externally by another organisation (E).
- not applicable – this system does not have central servers (N)

System Name	%	Location (U / P / E/ N)

Possible system change

8. How interested would you be in evaluating a new CDMS system in the next 18 months, to replace some or all of your existing systems? Please tick the appropriate category.

Not interested	Possibly interested	Definitely Interested

Part B: Specific questions about VISTA Trials deployment

Within the currently EU-funded ECRIN-IA project, EORTC is developing Vista Trials, a Clinical Data Management System (CDMS) for multinational clinical trials. Vista Trials is based on the existing CDMS developed and used by EORTC. The new Vista Trials is expected to be available in 2015. VISTA Trials will be available using a “Software As A Service” or SaaS model. This means that the system will not be made available for local installation. Instead the system and all data will be hosted centrally, and made available to trials units over the web.

Initially the system will be directly managed by EORTC, with a central installation at servers residing at EORTC HQ in Brussels. Later, when more computing resources are required (for more users) a third party certified data centre will be used.

This part of the survey is designed to find out how acceptable such an arrangement would be to trials units, and what factors would be important in making the system more or less attractive to potential customers.

9. Are there national, local or institutional rules and regulations that would **prevent** you using an externally hosted service, as described above?

- Yes (please specify the regulations or rules and their main impact below)
- No
- Unknown (needs to be clarified)

If you answered Yes please give the details here

10. If you were to use Vista Trials, would the proposed deployment model be a viable option for your own usage?

- No
- Yes

11. If you answered 'No' to Q10 please provide the main reasons for your response. Some possible concerns are listed below (please tick all that apply)

- Worries about the security of the data
- Concern over total costs, compared to installation locally
- Fears we might lose control over data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)
- As a matter of principle or policy, we do not want our data stored by another organisation
- Uncertainties about compliance with data protection requirements
- Other (please specify)

11b. If you ticked any of the boxes in Q11, please indicate below any actions, procedures or arrangements, from EORTC or ECRIN, that would reduce or eliminate your concerns.

12. If you answered 'Yes' to Q10 please provide your unit's views of the EORTC based SaaS deployment model described for Vista Trials? (please tick all that apply)

- The model is essential for us because we have no local IT systems; including hosting with Vista Trials makes the system an attractive option
- The model is not essential but would make the system more attractive to us than a system we needed to support directly ourselves
- The model presents no problem – we would evaluate Vista like any other CDMS system.
- The model would make the system less attractive to us – but we would still be willing to investigate Vista Trials as a potential system
- The model would allow us to try out the system for a few trials but for long term use we would want to move the system 'in-house'. (Please note – local installation of Vista Trials is not currently planned as an option)
- Other (please specify)

13. What factors would be the most important in making the proposed deployment for Vista Trials attractive to you? (please tick all that apply)

- Cheaper costs of SaaS versus local installation
- Convenience of outsourcing system management
- Ease of experimenting with / assessing the system
- Clear assurances and information on data security
- The option of local installation after initial trials of the system (Please note – local installation of Vista Trials is not currently planned as an option)
- Clear assurances and information on data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)
- Assurances of confidentiality of data
- Other (please specify)

14. Which of the following would you see as essential before considering using Vista Trials as SaaS (please tick all that apply)

- Service Level Agreements (SLAs) backed up by liabilities/penalties
- Compliance of SaaS service provider with the host's national regulatory standards
- The possibility of performing external audit of the SaaS provider by any Vista Trials user
- Other (please specify)

15. What type of license pricing model would you prefer? Please assume there were agreed ways to measure the selected quantities (please tick one only).

- A single standard licence (i.e. independent of usage)
- User fee model proposing small-medium-large packages. Each package will allow Vista Trials to be used for a maximum number of clinical studies and/or recruited patients per year.
- Licence fees calculated from the number of trials on the system
- Licence fees calculated from the number of CRF-data pages/items on the system
- Other (please specify)

16. A Committee, consisting of an equal number of representatives from EORTC and ECRIN, will be responsible for updated specifications, proposed modifications, further version releases and the non-profit fees. Would that help to make the deployment model more attractive for you?

- Yes
- No

17. ECRIN users will be invited to provide feedback on their use of VISTA Trials and to suggest improvement of the system after the ECRIN-IA project. Are you interested to contribute to such process?

- Yes
- No

18. User support is an important component of a software package. User support for VISTA will include access to helpdesk, on-site training and online training material. If ECRIN was involved in user support (e.g. first level support) would that make the deployment model more attractive for you?

- Yes
- No

19. Please select your favourite option for user support:

- User support is included in the user fee as a package (with some limitations on the maximum number of face to face trainings and communications with the helpdesk)
- Pay-for-usage model based on a price per unit e.g. face to face training, helpdesk communications (i.e. cost per ticket).

20. Are there any other points you would like to add about the deployment model and options you would like to see for Vista Trials?

Appendix 3 – Detailed Survey Results

A. Response to survey

Country	Units invited N	Units responded N	Response rate* %
Austria	5	1	
Czech Republic	7	3	
Denmark	4	-	
France	5	2	
Germany	20	15	75
Hungary	2	2	
Ireland	4	1	
Italy	4	1	
Luxemburg	1	-	
Netherlands	5	5	
Norway	5	-	
Poland	2	-	
Portugal	2	2	
Serbia	12	-	0
Spain	4	1	
Sweden	2	2	
Switzerland	9	4	
Turkey	4	3	
UK	32	11	34
Total	129	53	41

Table 1: Response per country. *percentages only for countries with more than 10 responding units

B. Data management activity of trial units

Recruitment Target*	Trials N (%)
0-50	389 (28)
51-200	412 (29)
201-1000	445 (32)
>1000	141(10)
Total	1404

Table 2: Involvement in current data management trials dependent on recruitment target
(Q3. Concerning your current data management trials, how many have recruitment targets of ...).

*17 units with missing data

Year	Trials / Year	Trial units N (%)
2012*	< 5	21 (46)
	5-9	11 (24)
	>= 10	14 (30)
	total	46 (100)
2013**	<5	20 (43)
	5-9	12 (26)
	>= 10	15 (32)
	total	47 (100)

Table 3: Frequency of DM trials started in 2012 and 2013 by trial units

(Q4. How many data management trials did you start in each of the following years?) *7 units had missing data for 2012, **6 units had missing data for 2013

Trials started in each year*		2013			
		<5	5-9	>=10	Total
2012	< 5	16	5	0	21
	5-9	3	6	2	11
	>= 10	1	1	12	14
	Total	20	12	15	46

Table 4: Comparison of number of DM trials started in 2012 versus 2013 by the trial units.

Each entry in a cell of the cross table corresponds to one trial unit. *7 units missing with data for 2012 and/or 2013. From the trial units, who reported figures for 2012 and 2013 (n= 46), 16+6+12=34 (74%) had a similar workload in 2012 and 2013.

Year	Num. of Subjects	Trial units N (%)
2012*	< 100	10 (28)
	100-499	9 (25)
	500-999	8 (22)
	>= 1000	9 (25)
	Total	36 (100)
2013**	<100	10 (27)
	100-499	9 (24)
	500-999	8 (22)
	>= 1000	10 (27)
	Total	37 (100)

Table 5: Number of subjects recruited in DM trials in 2012 and 2013

(Q5. How many subjects did you recruit in the following years within your DM trials?). *17 units had missing data in 2012, **16 units had missing data in 2013

Subjects recruited		2013				
		<100 N	100-499 N	500-999 N	>=1000 N	Total N
2012	<100	8	2	0	0	10
	100-499	1	7	1	0	9
	500-599	0	0	5	3	8
	>= 1000	0	0	2	7	9
	Total	10	9	8	10	37

Table 6: Comparison of number of recruited subjects in a trial unit in DM trials in 2012 versus 2013. Each entry in a cell of the cross table corresponds to one trial unit. With respect to our classification, three quarter of the trial units (27/36) had a comparable distribution of the number of recruited subjects between 2012 and 2013. *16 units had missing data for 2012 and/or 2013

Number of DM staff*	Trial units N (%)
1-5	40 (80)
6-10	7 (14)
11-20	1 (2)
>20	2 (4)
Total	50 (100)

Table 7: Number of staff working as data managers in trial units
(Q6. How many staff do you have working as data managers (FE)? This would exclude purely IT staff). *3 units had missing data

C. Clinical Data Management Systems (CDMS) in use

CDMS Data*	Systems listed			Location provided		Usage provided (as %age)	
	Units N	Units %	Systems N	Units N	Systems N	Units N	Systems N
1 system	25	53	25	25	25	25	25
2 systems	12	26	24	11	22	9	18
3 systems	6	13	18	6	18	6	18
4 systems	3	6	12	3	12	2	8
5 systems	1	2	5	1	5	1	5
Total	47	100	84	46	82	43	74

Table 8: Clinical database management systems used in trial units (Q7. Which CDMS do you currently use?*) *4 units with missing data, 2 units explicitly stated they had no CDMS.

System name	System Type*	Units Using	Installation Location		
			Own unit	Parent Univ./ Hospital	Externally Hosted
Access	G	4	3	1	
Access + SQL	G	1		1	
ALEA	C	2			2
Castor	C	1			1
Cerner Discovere	C	1			1
Cleanweb	C	2		1	1
Clincase	C	1		1	
ClinicOnline eTrials	C	1			1
Clinspire	C	1	1		
ERT	C	1			1
Excel	G	2	1		1
Incaplus	K	1			1
In-house	H	12	6	5	1
Janus	K	1		1	
KeyPoint eCRF	C	1	1		
LabKey	S	1			1
Leica Distiller	C	1		1	
LimeSurvey	S	2	1	1	
Macro	C	12	6	4	2
Marvin**	C	2		1	
Omnicom eClinical	C	4	1	1	2
OpenClinica	S	7	3	2	2
Oracle Clinical	C	3	2	1	
Oracle Forms	G	1	1		
Other (not specified)**	K	3			2
PheedIt	C	1	1		
RedCap**	S	6	2	2	1
SecuTrial	C	5	2	3	
Share Point	G	1		1	
Sintras	S	1	1		
SS.NET	K	1			1
webspirit	C	1	1		
Total		84	33	27	21
Location Percentage			41%	33%	26%

Table 9: Systems currently in use with the location of their installation

*code for system type: C= commercial, S= open source, G = general tools, H= in-house, K = unknown type of system. **One location was missing for Marvin and RedCap. One system under "Other" had location "not applicable"

System Type	Units Using N (%)	Installation Location		
		Own unit N	Parent Univ./ Hospital N	Externally Hosted N
General tool	9 (11)	5	3	1
Commercial	40 (48)	15	13	11
Open source	17 (20)	7	5	4
Inhouse	12 (14)	6	5	1
Unknown	6 (7)	0	1	4
Total	84	33	27	21
		41%	33%	26%

Table 10: Type of systems currently in use with location of use.

*3 locations missing (1 one open source tool, 1 commercial tool, 1 other)

System name	System Type*	Units Using N	Installation Location		
			Own unit N	Parent Univ./ Hospital N	Externally Hosted N
Access	G	2	2		
ClinicOnline eTrials	C	1			1
Clinspire	C	1	1		
ERT	C	1			1
In-house	H	11	6	4	1
Macro	C	10	5	3	2
Marvin	C	1		1	
Omnicom eClinical	C	3	1	1	1
OpenClinica	S	3	1	2	
Oracle Clinical	C	2	2		
PheedIt	C	1	1		
RedCap	S	1	1		
SecuTrial	C	2	2		
Share Point	G	1		1	
		40	22	12	6
			55%	30%	15%

Table 11: Systems currently in use for more than 50% of any unit's studies with location of use.

*Code for system type: C = commercial, S= open source, G = general tools, H= in-house, K = unknown type of system

System Type	Units Using N (%)	Installation Location		
		Own unit N	Parent Univ./ Hospital N	Externally Hosted N
General tool	3 (8)	2	1	0
Commercial	22 (55)	12	5	5
Open source	4 (10)	2	2	0
Inhouse	11 (28)	6	4	1
Unknown	0 (0)	0	0	0
Total	40	22	12	6
		55%	30%	15%

Table 12: Type of systems currently in use for more than 50% of any unit’s with location of use.

D. Interest in a new system

Level of Interest	Trial units* N (%)
Not interested	14 (27)
Possibly interested	24 (47)
Definitely interested	13 (25)
Total	51 (100)

Table 13: Interest of trial units to evaluate a new CDMS system in the next 18 months
*(Q8. How interested would you be in evaluating a new CDMS system in the next 18 months, to replace some or all of your systems?). *2 units had missing data*

E. Regulations on External Hosting

Response	N* (%)
Yes	10 (19)
No	23 (44)
Unknown	19 (37)
Total	52 (100)

Table 14: Rules and regulations preventing external hosting

*(Q9. Are there any national, local or institutional rules and regulations that would prevent you using an externally hosted service?). *1 unit had missing data*

Around 1/5 of those who answered this question reported issues with rules and regulations for an external hosted service (19%). The reasons given by those who answered yes, are the following:

- hosting outside EU (n=2)
- local rules of university/hospital (n=2)
- sponsor requirements (n=1)
- data protection laws (n=3)
- ISO requirements (n=1)
- GCP (n=1)

Three units reporting “unknown” to this question, gave additional comments:

- reassurance on security and access to data critical (n=1)
- in house policy (n=1)
- data protection and data security issues to be clarified (n=1)

Country	Yes	No	Unknown	Total
Switzerland		1	2	3
Czech Republic	1	2		3
Germany	1	7	7	15
Netherlands	3	1	1	5
Turkey		1	2	3
United Kingdom	3	3	5	11

Table 15: Views on Rules and regulations preventing external hosting within selected countries (Q9).

F. Viability of SaaS deployment Model

Response	N* (%)
Yes	27 (53)
No	24 (47)
Total	51 (100)

Table 16: Assessment of the proposed deployment model

(Q10. If you were to use VISTA trials, would the deployment model be a viable option for your own usage?). *2 units had missing data

		Q10. Proposed deployment model a viable option for your own usage?*		
		Yes N	No N	Total N
Q8. Interest in evaluating a new CDMS system in the next 18 months*	not interested	3	11	14
	possibly interested	12	11	23
	definitely interested	12	1	13
	Total	27	23	50

Table 17: Comparison of question 8 and question 10.

*3 units had missing data for question 8 and/or question 10

			Q10. Proposed deployment model a viable option for your own usage?*		
			Yes N	No N	Total N
Q4. How many data management trials did you start in each of the following years?	2012	0-4	14	7	21
		5-10	5	6	11
		>=10	4	9	13
		Total	23	22	45
	2013	0-4	12	8	20
		5-10	7	5	12
		>=10	5	9	14
		Total	24	22	46

Table 18: Comparison of question 4 and question 10.

*8 units with missing data for question 4 (2012) and/or question 10; 7 units with missing data for question 4 (2013) and/or question 10.

			Q10. Proposed deployment model a viable option for your own usage?*		
			Yes N	No N	Total N
Q5. Approximately how many subjects did you recruit in each of the following years within your data-management trials?	2012	<100	7	2	9
		100-499	4	5	9
		500-999	5	2	7
		>=1000	2	7	9
		Total	18	16	34
	2013	<100	7	2	9
		100-499	5	4	9
		500-999	3	5	8
		>=1000	4	5	9
		total	19	16	35

Table 19: Comparison of question 5 and question 10.

*19 units with missing data for question 5 (2012) and/or question 10; 18 units with missing data for question 5 (2013 and/or question 10)

		Q10. Proposed deployment model a viable option for your own usage?*		
		Yes N	No N	Total N
Q6. How many staff do you have working as data managers?	1-5	21	17	38
	6-10	3	4	7
	11-20	1	0	1
	>20	0	2	2
	Total	25	23	48

Table 20: Comparison of question 6 and question 10.

*5 units with missing data for question 6 and/or question 10

G. Factors influencing views of deployment

Response	N (%)
Worries about the security of the data	15 (63)
Concern over total costs, compared to installation locally	11 (46)
Fears we might lose control over data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)	13 (54)
As a matter of principle or policy, we do not want our data stored by another organisation	13 (54)
Uncertainties about compliance with data protection requirements	12 (50)
Other	10 (42)
Total	24

Table 21: Reasons for not accepting the proposed deployment model as a viable option (Q11. If you answered “no” to question 10 please provide the main reasons for your response. Some possible concerns are listed below)

Q11b. Actions, procedures or arrangements, from EORTC or ECRIN, that would reduce or eliminate your concerns
More information about costs (n = 1)
Flexible access to data + reassurance on security/confidentiality (n =1)
More information on staffing, software updates (n= 1)
More information on costs + flexible access to data (n =1)
Bound by UK law (n =1)
No possible solutions (n=1)
Satisfied with existing system (n=2)
Proof of support of full trial life cycle by EORTC + commitment for development, support and finances for a longer period (n=1)
Participation of nationwide regulatory bodies and EMA, authorized access to data only (n = 1)
Reconciliation with German privacy regulation (n = 1)
Creation of a data centre in France (n =1)
SLAs + vendor audits (n = 1)
Answered by question 13 and 14 (n = 1)
Local installation in own unit (n = 1)

Table 22: Actions, procedures or arrangements that would reduce or eliminate concerns

Response	N (%)
The model is essential for us because we have no local IT systems; including hosting with Vista Trials makes the system an attractive option	8 (30)
The model is not essential but would make the system more attractive to us than a system we needed to support directly ourselves	6 (22)
The model presents no problem – we would evaluate Vista like any other CDMS system.	14 (52)
The model would make the system less attractive to us – but we would still be willing to investigate Vista Trials as a potential system	6 (22)
The model would allow us to try out the system for a few trials but for long term use we would want to move the system 'in-house'. (Please note – local installation of Vista Trials is not currently planned as an option)	3 (11)
Other	3 (11)
Total	27

Table 23: Views from trial units accepting the SaaS deployment model described for VISTA trials
(Q12. If you answered “yes” to question 10 please provide your unit’s views of the EORTC based SaaS deployment model described for VISTA Trials)

Response	N* (%)
Cheaper costs of SaaS versus local installation	27 (53)
Convenience of outsourcing management	19 (37)
Ease of experimenting with/assessing the system	20 (39)
Clear assurances and information on data security	38 (75)
The option of local installation after initial trials of the system (Please note – local installation of Vista Trials is not currently planned as an option)	17 (33)
Clear assurances and information on data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)	34 (67)
Assurances of confidentiality of data	36 (71)
Other	11 (22)
Total	51

Table 24: Factors making the proposed deployment model more attractive.
(Q13. What factors would be the most important in making the proposed deployment for VITSA trials attractive to you?). *2 units had missing data.

Q13. The most important factors in making the proposed deployment for VISTA trials attractive to you?	Q10. Proposed deployment model a viable option for your own usage?*		
	Yes N	No N	Total N
Cheaper costs of SaaS versus local installation	18	8	26
Convenience of outsourcing management	16	2	18
Ease of experimenting with/assessing the system	12	8	20
Clear assurances and information on data security	22	15	37
The option of local installation after initial trials of the system	8	9	17
Clear assurances and information on data access (e.g. for inspection, analysis)	18	15	33
Assurances of confidentiality of data	19	16	35
Other	4	7	11
Total			51

Table 25 Comparison of question 10 and 13

*3 units with missing data

Response	N* (%)
Service Level Agreements (SLAs) backed up by liabilities/penalties	39 (78)
Compliance of SaaS service provider with the host's national regulatory standard	40 (80)
The possibility of performing external audit of the SaaS provider by any Vista Trials user	30 (60)
Other	6 (12)
Total	50

Table 26: Prerequisites for using VISTA trials as SaaS (14. Which of the following would you see as essential before considering VISTA trials as SaaS?). *3 units had missing data

		Q10. Proposed deployment model a viable option for your own usage?*		
		yes N	No N	Total N
14. Which of the following would you see as essential before considering VISTA trials as SaaS?	Service Level Agreements (SLAs) backed up by liabilities/penalties	21	17	38
	compliance of SaaS service provider with the host's national regulatory standard	23	16	39
	the possibility of performing external audit of the SaaS provider by any Vista Trials user	19	11	30
	other	0	6	6

Table 27: Comparison of question 10 and 14. *4 units with missing data

H. Licensing

Response	N* (%)
A single standard licence (i.e. independent of usage)	24 (48)
User fee model proposing small-medium-large packages. Each package will allow Vista Trials to be used for a maximum number of clinical studies and/or recruited patients per year.	9 (18)
Licence fees calculated from the number of trials on the system	9 (18)
Licence fees calculated from the number of CRF-data pages/items on the system	5 (10)
Other	3 (6)
Total	50

Table 28: Preference of trial units for license pricing models

(15. What type of licensing pricing model would you prefer? Please assume that there were agreed ways to measure the selected quantities). *3 units had missing data

I. Role of ECRIN

Response	N* (%)
Yes	31 (60)
No	21 (40)
Total	52

Table 29: Role of the CDMS-Committee for the attractiveness of the deployment model

(16. A Committee, consisting of an equal number of representatives from EORTC and ECRIN, will be responsible for updated specifications, proposed modifications, further version releases and the non-profit fees. Would that help to make the deployment model more attractive for you?).

*1 unit with missing data

Response	N* (%)
Yes	36 (72)
No	14 (28)
Total	50

Table 30: Interest of trial units in providing feedback on the use of VISTA (Q17. ECRIN users will

be invited to provide feedback on their use of VISTA Trials and to suggest improvement of the system after the ECRIN-IA project. Are you interested to contribute to such process?).

*3 units had missing data

Response	N* (%)
Yes	33 (63)
No	19 (37)
Total	52

Table 31: Attractiveness of involvement of ECRIN in user support (Q18. User support is an

important component of a software package. User support for VISTA will include access to helpdesk, on-site training and online training material. If ECRIN was involved in user support (e.g. first level support) would that make the deployment model more attractive for you?).

*1 unit with missing data

Response	N* (%)
User support is included in the user fee as a package (with some limitations with the helpdesk)	42 (84)
Pay-for-usage model based on a price per unit e.g. face to face training, helpdesk communications (i.e. cost per ticket).	8 (16)
Total	50

Table 32: Favourite option for user support

(Q19. Please select your favourite option for user support).

*3 units with missing data

J. General Comments

In question 20 trial units were given the opportunity to add any other points about the deployment model and options they would like to see for VISTA trials. Here the comments/statements from 18 trial units were received and are listed (shortened version from free text entry):

- concerns losing control of system features
- additional features for randomisation, query management, PRO-management, follow-up schedule
- ECRIN-ERIC committee attractive but danger of delay of updates, integration of patient/trial management tool
- no demand currently but wish for regular information on the system, including prices
- support for web services (import/export)
- option for open source and community involvement
- ECRIN should not advocate one system and should be independent
- outsourcing requires validation package
- development roadmap lead by user group rather than vendor + long term commitment for license costs + integration with API/web service + download of data in real time
- questions about storage of data after finishing a study, costs, individual data interfaces (web services), APIs, international encoding and special characters, assess to VISTA database scheme, possibility to configure individual parameters (e.g. date)
- freezer management system or tool
- open source community responsible for updates + releases + non-profit fees
- positive arguments for SaaS model in principle + problems with implementation in large organization
- additional features: annotated CRF, export routines, query management, data import, audit log, certification process + service availability
- independent audits + maybe alternative for RedCap
- missing information about VISTA: functional restrictions, import/export, customizable reports, interfaces to data coding systems, data entry by patients, trial specific workflows, triggered emails
- local installation instead of SaaS
- preference for single licence with no limitations